

**Accord University
Knowledge & Vision**

**PROJECT COMMUNICATION AND PERFORMANCE OF DIGFER GENERAL
TEACHING HOSPITAL CONSTRUCTION IN
MOGADISHU - SOMALIA**

THIS DISSERTATION IS SUBMITTED AS PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE
REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF THE MASTER OF PROJECT
MANAGEMENT FROM ACCORD UNIVERSITY – SOMALIA.

DEPARTMENT OF SOCIAL SCIENCES

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22-JAN-2023

DECLARATION

This research report is my original work and has not been presented for a Master's Degree or any other Academic Award in any University or Institution of Learning.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Shukri', is placed on a light blue rectangular background.

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Date: 22-JAN-2023

APPROVAL

I confirm that the work in this research report was done by the candidate under my supervision.

Signature of Supervisor

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DR MOHAMMAD MAHMOUD ABU OMAR Ph.D.

DEDICATION

To the almighty Allah, Thank you for instilling wisdom and giving me a sense of direction and purpose throughout my entire life. To my parents I warmly appreciate you for your enormous contribution to my life including the academic one, this appreciation goes to my father Mr. Abdi Karim Said Adam and my mother Mrs. Nadifo Moalim Mohamud most importantly for everything support accorded to me, may Allah bless you.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

At first I am grateful to ALLAH for giving me strength to complete my master's thesis.

I would like to acknowledge my supervisor **Dr. Mohammad Mahmoud** for the guidance, suggestions and constant support on this study. Your assistance has been instrumental.

My special appreciation goes to my entire family most especially my mother Mrs. Nadifo Moalim Mohamud and my father Mr. Abdi Karim Said Adam and my sister Fatima Abdikarim for their love and support they have offered me.

My Special thanks go to my best friend Mr. Abdikadir Ibrahim with whom I weathered through the storms, giving each other encouragement and for their positive criticism.

May Allah Reward You All.

LIST OF ACRONYMS

B.Sc.....	Bachelor of Science
B.Tech.....	Bachelor of Technology
CEOs.....	Chief Education Officers
GNP.....	Gross National Product
HND.....	Higher National Diploma
M.Sc.....	Masters of Science
M.Tech.....	Masters of Technology
ND.....	National Diploma
SSPSS.....	Statistical Package for Social Sciences
UK.....	United Kingdom
UNDP.....	United Nations Development Program
UNRWA.....	United Nations Relief and Works Agency
WBS.....	Work Break Down Structure
WBS.....	Work Breakdown Structure

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to examine the project communication and Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu. It was guided by four objectives, that included i) to assess the impact of formal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu –Somalia; ii). to assess the impact of informal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu –Somalia; iii) to examine the influence of communication channels on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu and iv) to establish the relationship between project communication and performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu. This study was guided by the Diffusion of Innovations Theory. Diffusion of innovations is a theory that seeks to explain how, why, and at what rate new ideas and technology are spread. The study comprised of a population of 149 respondents from which a sample size of 109 respondents were selected, and a descriptive research design was used to collect data from 109 respondents using self-administered questionnaires as the main data collection instrument. The findings of this study were; that the effect between formal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu -Somalia was rated good and this was indicated by the overall mean of 2.97, implying that there is a formalized system intended to help the Digfer general teaching hospital construction on how plans are drawn after consulting the members, furthermore with respect to the effect of Informal Communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu -Somalia, this rated good and this was indicated by the average mean of 2.79, hence implying that Informal Communication is carried out and always assessed well in order to improve project effectiveness. The researcher concluded that; formal communication strongly affects the performance of professionals within the Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu –Somalia. Therefore, clearly establishing and managing the structures of formal communication on project must always be on the agenda of team leaders and management before the commencement of every project. Recommendations based on findings were that; Although there were clear distinction between the agreements and disagreements of the formal communication, it is therefore recommended that Digfer General Teaching Hospital Construction, formal communication should be compared with traditional communication tools based on criteria for efficient communication.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

This chapter deals with background of the study, statement of the problem, objectives, research questions, hypothesis, and significance of the study, scope and operational definitions of key terms.

1.1 Background of the Study

1.1.1 Historical perspective

Globally, the performance of most construction projects in European countries like; Italy, France, Spain, Germany, etc. has undoubtedly been based on the experience, and technical expertise of project managers as they tend to add value to projects by delivering successful projects in terms of agreed project objectives due to the fact that project management processes are geared towards the delivery of successful projects (Zulu, 2017). Thus such performance has been attributed to; Leadership skills for project manager, Availability of personals with high experience and qualification, Availability of resources as planned through project duration, learning from best practice and experience of others (Belout *et al.*, 2014).

In countries like Iraq, construction projects suffer from problems and complex issues in performance such as cost, quality and safety, as many projects tend to be delayed and thus the actual cost are much more than the values because of the security conditions. Ahadzie, (2013), argues that the core difference between very successful projects and less successful projects is in the ability of project manager's development of interpersonal skills. In UK, most project managers execute decision making and building efficient mutual relationships among a diverse group of project stakeholders (Ahadzie, 2015).

In African countries like; Ghana, Nigeria, Egypt, Morocco, Tunisia, etc the construction industry is complex in its nature because it comprises large numbers of parties as owners (clients), contractors, consultants, stakeholders, and regulators. Despite this complexity, the industry plays a major role in the development and achievement of society's goals. It is one of the largest industries and contributes to about 10% of the gross national product (GNP) in industrialized

countries (Navon, 2005). Project performance can be measured and evaluated using a large number of performance indicators that could be related to various dimensions (groups) such as time. However, many local construction projects report poor performance due to many evidential project-specific causes such as: unavailability of materials; excessive amendments of design and drawings; poor coordination among participants, ineffective monitoring and feedback, and lack of project leadership skills (UNRWA 2016). The ever-important macro-level political and economic factors have also been related to poor projects performance (UNRWA 2016 & 2017). Similarly, Iyer and Jha (2005) identified many factors as having influence on project cost performance, these include: project manager's competence, top management support, project manager's coordinating and leadership skills, monitoring and feedback by the participants, decision-making, coordination among project participants, owners' competence, social condition, economic condition, and climatic condition.

In East Africa, achieving successful project performance in construction projects is still a challenge in counties like Uganda, Tanzania, Kenya, and Rwanda, though it can be improved through proper Project communication which clarifies project task and enables stakeholders to be wholly involved in the projects. However, despite the importance of project communication many projects in higher institutions have not performed to their expectations.

In Somalia, the construction industry plays a main role in transforming the aspirations and the needs of its people into reality by implementing various physical structures. A construction project is commonly acknowledged as successful when it is completed on time, within budget, and in accordance with specifications and to stakeholder's satisfaction (Cornelissen, 2016). The success of a construction project depends on its performance, Sudan construction industry is facing several problems and challenges this can be summarized in availability of poorness in the performance of construction projects.

Thus for Construction projects in Mogadishu to performance better, they require skilled management, as they are complicated and face many challenges and constraints, such as cost, time regulations, materials and environmental rules or customs. In construction 29 projects several activities happen and take place at the same time, but still are connected and integrated. Therefore we need thorough and effective communications and cooperation to manage and control these activities (Walker- 2017).

Project Communication has been found to be an element in engaging performance of construction projects which involves defined objectives that must be achieved and numerous resources which need to be efficiently utilized. The need for participants' communication in construction project delivery to develop and use tools to improve their efficiency and effectiveness in project delivery was emphasized in UK and Sweden (Robinson *et al.*, 2015). This is because communication brings about good Coordination among project staff, and project managers as it entirely influences on cost performance (Iyer and Jha, 2016). Chan, Scott and Chan (2004) examined factors affecting the success of a construction project. Five major groups of independent variables, namely project related factors, project procedures, project management actions, human related factors, and external environment were identified as crucial to project success.

1.2 Statement of the problem

One of the most serious barriers that projects face is to resolve the problem of information flow upwards, downwards, and sideways which is often grandly termed communication (Bennett *et al.*, 2013). Ideally the unfortunate, use of communication as medium to resolve construction and design problems are essential, in order to fully appreciate the problem of communication in Somalia. Nevertheless it is believed that Digfer general teaching hospital construction experience a number of defects as result of poor communication (Bernard, 2012). For example, the project involves poorly detailed drawing, operatives being given incorrect instructions or technical information not being available. However, what is not known is how project professionals collect and disseminate timely information when working on a project in Somalia. Unfortunately the project performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction ranks below standards since it has challenges related to completion time, out of scope, over shoot budgets, short of quality expectations, and in the extreme cases they have faced total shut down (Bissah *et al.*, 2013). This study therefore seeks to establish the impact that project communication has on project performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu.

1.3 General Objective

The general objective of the study was to examine the impact of project communication on Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu.

1.4 Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of the study included the following:

- i). To assess the impact of formal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu -Somalia.
- ii). To assess the impact of informal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu -Somalia.
- iii). To examine the influence of communication channels on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu.
- iv). To establish the relationship between project communication and performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu.

1.5 Research Questions

This study seeked to answer the following research questions:

- i). What is the impact of formal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu, Somalia?
- ii). What is the impact of informal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu –Somalia?
- iii). What is the influence of communication channels on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu?
- iv). What is the relationship between project communication and performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu?

1.6 Hypotheses

- i). There is a significant relationship between formal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu, Somalia?
- ii). There is a significant relationship between informal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu –Somalia?
- iii). There is a significant relationship between communication channels on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu.

1.7 Significance of the Study

The study will provide a reliable local source of literature for further studies on the concept of project communication and performance especially in developing countries like Somalia where there is still inadequate research on such a topical concept.

The study will benefit both policy makers by enhancing their understanding of the interrelationship of soft factors like project communication and commitment as prerequisites to achieving envisaged project outcomes and the eventual advancement of performance indicators for efficient project management.

Future researchers will benefit from the new body of knowledge created by this study. This work will form part of the literature review for those who would be researching on project communication and performance.

The study will also help the researcher acquire new knowledge which enable him find best ways of enhancing social development in Mogadishu through supporting infrastructural development.

This will enable government and non-government agencies to be more relevant to the needs of their targeted beneficiaries, with the establishment of community health facilities to offer subsidized health care to the people in the community.

Furthermore, the study will also benefit the project beneficiaries living in Mogadishu, through catering for their health needs since the project is extended to their communities.

1.8 Scope of the Study

1.8.1 Content Scope

This study was set to assess the impact of formal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu –Somalia, to assess the impact of informal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu – Somalia and to examine the influence of communication channels on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu, and to establish the relationship between project communication and performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu.

1.8.2 Geographical Scope

This study was carried out in the Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu. The project is located in the heart of Mogadishu; the capital city of Somalia. The researcher conducted the study from Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu because of its decline in the project performance (Ghalib, Jama Mohamed, 2014).

1.8.3 Time scope

The study focused on 2010-2018 because it is during this time period that there were increased cases of poor project communication hence contributing to poor project performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction (Emmitt, S. *et al.*, 2017). The study took Six months that is from May to October 2019.

1.9 Definitions of Key Terms

For the purpose of this study, the following terms are defined as they are used in the study:

Project communication is two-way process of reaching mutual understanding, in which participants not only exchange (encode-decode) information, news, ideas and feelings but also create and share meaning in the project (Bosch and Philips, 2013).

Project performance, It is the measure to which a project achieves its desired objectives considering the time and resource constraints (Brown, 2011).

Project, Is a sequence of tasks. Planned from the beginning to the end, Bound by time, Resources, and required results (Burek, 2012).

A **teaching hospital** is a hospital or medical center that provides medical education and training to future and current health professionals and that is involved in medical research. Teaching hospitals are often affiliated with medical schools and work closely with medical students throughout their period of matriculation, and especially during their clerkship (internship) years. In most cases, teaching hospitals also offer Graduate Medical Education (GME)/ physician residency programs, where medical school graduates train under a supervising (attending) physician to assist with the coordination of care (Browne, 2012).

Construction is the process of constructing a building or infrastructure. Construction differs from manufacturing in that manufacturing typically involves mass production of similar items without

a designated purchaser, while construction typically takes place on location for a known client. Construction as an industry comprises six to nine percent of the gross domestic product of developed countries. Construction starts with planning, design, and financing; it continues until the project is built and ready for use (Halpin, *et al.*, 2010).

1.10 Conceptual framework

Figure 1.1: Showing the Conceptual Framework

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

Literature review is a partial summary of the previous work related to the hypothesis of the study that was explored and cited as well as existing knowledge related to project communication and project performance in correlation to the research specific objectives.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by **Diffusion of innovations theory** developed by **Everett Rogers in 1962**. The theory examines how ideas are spread among groups of people (Carlsson *et al.*, 2011). Diffusion goes beyond the two-step flow theory, centering on the conditions that increase or decrease the likelihood that an innovation, a new idea, product or practice, will be adopted by members of a given culture. Therefore this theory will help Top authorities of the Project, Project staff (Casual labourers), Project coordinators, Project supervisors and Project managers to communicate effectively with an essence of sharing innovative ideas in carrying technical work during the hospital construction process. In multi-step diffusion, the opinion leader still exerts a large influence on the behavior of individuals, called adopters, but there are also other intermediaries between the media and the audience's decision-making. One intermediary is the change agent, someone who encourages an opinion leader to adopt or reject an innovation (Cherry, 2012).

Innovations are not adopted by all individuals in a social system at the same time. Instead, they tend to adopt in a time sequence, and can be classified into adopter categories based upon how long it takes for them to begin using the new idea (Cul and Smith, 2011). Practically speaking, it's very useful for a change agent to be able to identify which category certain individuals belong to, since the short-term goal of most change agents is to facilitate the adoption of an innovation. Adoption of a new idea is caused by human interaction through interpersonal networks (Emmitt & Gorse, 2013). If the initial adopter of an innovation discusses it with two members of a given social system, and these two become adopters who pass the innovation along to two peers, and so on, the resulting distribution follows a binomial expansion.

The diffusion of innovation theory analyzes how the social members adopt the new project innovative ideas and how they made the decision towards it. Both mass media and interpersonal

communication channel is involved in the diffusion process. The theory heavily relies on Human capital. According to the theory, innovations should be widely adopted in order to attain development and sustainability after the completion of the project.

2.2 Review of Related Literature

2.2.1 Formal Communication and performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu –Somalia

Formal communication is a broad term that includes multiple communication channels. Tenhiälä and Salvador (2014) define formal communication as a standard protocol that describes when and what is being communicated and who is participating in the communication transaction. The formal communication is therefore traceable and is often beforehand known to the participants. Tang and Thomas (2015) extend Tenhiälä and Salvador's (2014) description and include rules, conventions and standard procedures through predetermined schedules, memos and management reports. The arrangement of formal internal communication is often determined from the top and specified in advance (Tang & Thomas, 2015). The formal internal communication can be further developed using a system that integrates the employees through a platform. This can be used as an automated version of a formal communication protocol (Tenhiälä & Salvador, 2014). Formal internal communication works as a facilitator for the mediation of information throughout the entire organization (Tang & Thomas, 2015), which sometimes makes large investments in internal communication systems necessary (Tenhiälä & Salvador, 2014). Lacking the necessary formal internal communication structure may lead to loss of information and therefore in the lack of enough teamwork.

Since the formal internal communication is traceable, a better understanding of the colleagues' knowledge becomes evident, which eases the cooperation (Tang & Thomas, 2015). However, all factors that Tenhiälä and Salvador (2014) mention in order for communication to be perceived as formal do not need to be present. An example of this is a regular meeting. Even though all the participants are unaware of the content beforehand, it is treated as formal since the time is known and it follows a standard protocol (Tenhiälä & Salvador, 2014).

Formal Communication plays an important role in for the success of any projects. In any successful project where project management appeared to be done, the capabilities of communication are the main factor for the project success (Müller & Turner, 2010).

Formal Communication in projects is very important for success, mainly for big projects. The more the larger and complex are, the more communication is significant for the final outcome (Olsson & Johansson, 2011). The communication processes of performance report, requested changes, forecasts, organizational process and updates (Olsson & Johansson, 2011). One fundamental process of communication is to exchange of information so, that it will socialize the employees by socialization, coordination and mutual understanding in the projects, since communication is „the nervous system of any organized group and the glue that hold organization together“ (Olsson & Johansson, 2011).

Maintaining effective formal Communication with the project team over time (Kimball and Rheingold, 2015), raises the quantity of social ties and the clustering co-efficient both directly and indirectly. This is Consistent with Zhong and Low’s (2019) findings that Changes driven by the Project management are usually unlikely to produce desired effects without coordination and support from a variety of personnel. Project managers however, are most times preoccupied with addressing the technical issues and fail on soft issues like proper functioning of informal communication. In the manufacturing sector, this phenomenon has largely been attributed to the fact that most project managers are often less informed in people matters and as such ignorant of the value inherent in properly managing people (Ruuska, 1996).

Intra-project formal communications enable Individual Project team members to perceive, interpret and get committed to inferences drawn from the project charter as a form of psychological contract Rousseau (1989). To concretize this argument, (Bentein *et al.*, 2010), defines Commitment as a “psychological stabilizing or obliging force that binds individuals to courses of action relevant” to the project. Thus, project team members will typically interpret the various intra-project communications and on which basis they will find a commensurate level of commitment to offer in return (Schein, 2010). This atmosphere of reciprocity can only be sustained if the project manager meets his part of the informal bargain. As long as the project delivers as expected by its stakeholders, they will remain committed to the project’s values otherwise

stakeholders may become less committed and dissociate themselves from the project (Gakovic & Tetric, 2013; Conway and Briner, 2002). According to Eisenberger *et al.* (2010), individuals who perceive that they are cared for, have not only higher levels of commitment, but are more conscious about their responsibilities, have greater involvement in the organization, and are more innovative. Therefore Project managers ought to communicate their support to their staff for the work that they do because this perceived support allows for more commitment to the project activities.

Successful project management communication is about being there for everyone, being in touch with the real challenges of the project, understanding the real issues within the team who must deliver the project as well as understanding the issues of the sponsors who the team delivers the project for (Oetzel, 2012). Being present, visible and engaged with everyone is important during the good times and the challenging times. Communication is not only about speaking to and hearing from people, it's about understanding the complete message.

Formal Communication goals are defined according to the interest of shareholders. During the execution of the project, the project managers' ability to communicate is crucial to the success of the project. One of the important tasks for the project managers is to communicate with the stakeholders (Tonnquist, 2010). Successful communication may not be always successful persuasion (Tonnquist, 2010) it is very important the basics of communication in order to exchange the right information. In the current dynamic environment, communication is still constant desirable for managing projects (Henderson, 2008, p. 48). The research study in this area by (Locovou *et al.*, 2019) demonstrate that quality communication comes from high project officials which can be credible, complete, accurate and timely information for the input of the project.

It has been discussed by (Beardsley *et al.*, 2012), about the role of formal communication; words express ideas, expressed emotions and attitude. One of the main differences of nonverbal communication is that the medium of formal verbal communication is neither vocalized nor written word, it is a complete mix of psychological responses, mix of behaviors and environmental interactions that can either relate with the conscious and unconscious interaction of peoples. Based on the finding of behavioral scientists, formal nonverbal communication is very significant in communication by contributing approximately 55%- 95% of communication from nonverbal expression. (Beardsley *et al.*, 2012,).

Müller & Turner, (2010) discuss about mutual exchange of information for exchange and finding the right level of information for communication. Accordingly, effective leaders facilitate subordinates to foster information by soliciting information, listening, evaluating different information, evaluate the collected information and finally discusses about it with the rest of employees.

It also argued that communication is not only limited to formal verbal communication, body language also plays significant role in the communication process. In the study made by Ekman (2004, cited in Müller & Turner, 2010) indicate that if the person is talking frankly, is trying to distort information, or even telling to lie, it can show well-known signal that can convey his/her attitude. Effective leaders give high valued for body languages and act to adjust their communication. Communication lies based on (Tonnuqvist, 2008) searching the right amount and type of information to communicate to the right party. Communication encompasses wide media coverage; it could be mass communication through Radio and TV, small size communication like meeting, committee discussion groups and large group-communication like speeches and lectures (Beardsley *et al.*, 2012). The communication means can able built the communication system of the project organization according to the argument of researchers.

Communication provides information regarding the extent to which members feel accepted as valued organizational colleagues (Smidts *et al.*, 2001). It can particularly affect employees' degree of identifying with an organization (Bartels *et al.*, 2017). Open and respectful communication will generate feelings of being part of a group as well as the feeling of self-esteem. Through such communication attributes, employees' willingness to identify with a company increases (Smidts *et al.*, 2011). This further underlines the importance of communication as it steers the shaping of performance in organizational members (Larson & Pepper, 2003). Furthermore, continual communication from management to employees, that is top-down, leads to common thoughts about the organization that additionally establishes members with the feeling of being part of and identifying with the organization (Chreim, 2012).

According to various modern researchers, the specific ways of formal communication in which performance is established through are much undiscovered or paid little attention to. Researchers pose the question of how, empirically, it can be investigated and also put it forward as an

interesting future research perspective (Chaput, Brummans & Cooren, 2011). This view is supported by other researchers that have studied the relationship between project communication and performance (Chen, Chi & Friedman, 2013; Bartels *et al.*, 2017; Millward, Haslam & Postmes, 2017; Bartels *et al.*, 2016). The need for investigating the role of formal internal communication in establishing strong performance in employees is therefore evident.

2.2.2 Informal Communication and performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu –Somalia

Informal communication means to learn in an atmosphere where a learner is directed to the communication process in informal setting. The learner learns in non-regular atmosphere. Tissot (2014) adds that this informal communication is concerned with the daily routine activities of work, with family or with friends or leisure time. The learner is not even sometimes aware of the fact that he/she is communication. This communication becomes the part of his other activities while with his/her family, leisure time and with his/her friends. This communication has neither any restrictions nor rules and regulations to be followed and it has no any specific time to be learnt, This form of communication is not limited to time, age, environment, ethnic background, occupation etc.

Communication which occurs in outside settings of the organization is termed ‘informal communication Maarschalk, (2018). Marsick, & Volpe (2017) Define informal communication as “communication that is un-structured based on experience and it is non-institutionalized.

There exist numerous studies that have paid attention to the lack of effective communication in the construction industry (Emerson, 1962; Banwell 1964; Latham, 1994; Egan 1998, 2002). Communication carries a special importance within the industry as a result of its project-based structure. Given that construction is such a fragmented, dynamic and disparate sector, effective communication becomes essential “for the successful delivery of performance goals (productivity, profitability and repeat working opportunities” (Dainty et.al, 2016). A review of management literature reveals that studies on communication have focused mainly on the nature of interpersonal communication. However, there seems to be few empirical studies related to the subject in project-based industries such as construction.

Informal communication in construction projects takes three forms: oral, written (or graphic), and nonverbal communication. Oral communication refers to sending messages by using common spoken symbols. It includes face-to-face, telephone, meetings, and presentations. In a project environment, it is the appropriate medium for “timely exchange of information, rapid feedback, immediate synthesis of message, and timely closure” Carlsson *et al.* (2011). Written communication includes e-mails, fax, memos, letters, reports, plans (strategic and tactical), legal documents and other forms of information to be transmitted. Writing bid proposals, progress reports, training manuals etc. is an important part of management of construction projects.

Jergeas and Hartman (2011) suggested keeping good records and communications in order to avoid claims and disputes in construction projects. Gorse *et.al.*, (1999) investigated interpersonal communication behavior between designers and contractors during the construction phase of projects. Their findings reveal that informal approaches such as face-to-face are perceived to be the most effective medium of communication within the industry. Their results are also supported by Carlsson *et al.*, (2011) who conducted communication research within the Swedish construction industry. Carlsson *et al.*, (2011) argue that “barriers to effective communication are likely to be broken down by more integrated project delivery systems. In their study, Shohet and Frydman (2013) identified effective patterns of communication at the construction manager level in projects delivered by construction management procurement protocol in Israel. They found that verbal communication continues to be highly important in ensuring adherence to project objectives. Furthermore, Culp and Smith (2001) argue that personality type plays an important.

According to Leslie, (2015) suggest that informal communication includes more than 70 percent of overall communication in any workplace. Informal communication environments are less structured systems as compared to the formal communication setup where learning is turned from trainers to the people in contact with learning process. Choi, (2011), Informal learning can also be named as experiential learning where this is learnt from experience or through experience. But according to French system, it is regulated and defined in legal terms. According to this system, skills, knowledge and competencies will result in certification and also applied to diplomas, certificates and titles etc. (Conlon, 2013) Informal learning is known to be the most important element of education for the learners of all ages.

According to Berg, (2008), Good evidence is found in this respect that many people are engaged in technology based informal learning either at their homes, the community and their work life (Cranmer, 2016). Felstead, (2019) Gave a conclusion in this field that the modern technology like computers and other forms of information technology keep the children and other people in contact with the experiences and activities that are supportive to learning processes but this form of learning is not in the traditionally made setup. In contrast to informal learning, there is formal learning which is according to Bristol, (2011), the environment which is under the supervision of curricula, teachers or trainers.

In the perspective of learner, informal learning is unintentional and does not result in certification. We can find much more definitions for informal learning to be quite similar to each other but the real difference is that the dependency of the study of informal learning on its quality side. This form of learning is un-intentional so it would be quite hard to assess it without certification. From the research of Gerber, (Bassi, 2012), it is clearly shown that the informal learning can be quantified while considering their informal learning activities but similar outcomes could not be generated in case of adults without modification.

According to Ruuska (2016), project communication acts as a connecting factor that links the various stakeholders of the projects like the Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu in Somalia, together and also the project to its environment *let alone* uniting its activities at different levels of development. Bian (2017) adds that the strength of the linkage (relationship) grows through a history of interactions in which members of a network develop friendship and trust. The above statement points to the fact that stronger relations in a network could be fostered through effective project communication over time. Herkt (2017) affirms that the project manager's major responsibility is to build supportive social networks (collaborative relationships) among a diverse group of stakeholders.

This is in agreement with the idea of Engwall, (2014), who emphasized that Communication plays an integral role in keeping a project on task, because project managers need to ensure that the team members and the stakeholders are informed of what you expect of them in terms of their roles and

responsibilities and other time constraints that prevent them from accomplishing the task on time. Thus as project managers, it's their task to keep them informed of project details and progress..."

Additionally, in agreement with the idea of Ruuska (2017) who clarified that project communication acts as a connecting factor that links the various stakeholders of the projects like the Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu in Somalia, together and also the project to its environment *let alone* uniting its activities at different levels of development, because at any time, there may be stakeholders who need information about the project such as the objectives, plan, risks, needs, and time constraints. Adherence to a system of regular and focused communication can prevent misunderstandings and delays that can cause failure of the Digfer general teaching hospital construction.

Fowler, Dawes, and Christakis (2019) and (Stacy, 2016) maintain that in social networks, some nodes develop more contacts (Higher Degree) than others and that the clustering coefficient (transitivity) also differs based on the level of interactions (communications) maintained. Although Boddy (2002), Herkt (2017) and (Scott, 2011) suggest that efficient social networks are those in which relationships have been reinforced and are dependable, that is, members enjoy close relationship (strong ties) and therefore highly trust each other, Granovater (2013) maintains that weak ties should never be sidestepped in favor of concretizing strong ties. This is because the constant interaction in strongties may with time bring in no new vital information (Granovater, 2013) which would have been cheaply sourced through tapping into the power lines of a variety of weakly linked social networks. These arguments seem to imply that the manager's role of disseminating information should extend to periphery players thereby stretching project scope as opposed to the project management best practice of delimiting scope (PMBOK Guide, 2010).

Sönderlund, (2012) noted that project managers like those handling the Digfer general teaching hospital construction In Mogadishu should be mindful of any cultural differences among team members and other stakeholders that could result in miscommunication. Modern business requires multicultural competency at every level, including project planning, to avoid costly errors in planning. Diverse teams may benefit from spending some time developing cultural awareness in effort to improve communication.

An essential starting point for communication is the development of an effective communication plan that defines the information needs of each stakeholder, who will communicate that information, and how it will be communicated (Sönderlund, 2012). Stakeholders must be encouraged to verbalize their concerns should they feel that communication is inadequate, and the project manager should have a proactive plan in place to monitor for signs of communication problems. Project planning must include accurate information concerning the project from every stakeholder to avoid programming flaws into the project from its beginning (Walker, 2012). An awareness of the requirements of the project, the capabilities of team members, and the resources available will go a long way to the development of a viable project plan that will deliver its desired outcome.

Communication may mean being able to talk, speak and be listened to. It can also be called interaction (World Bank, 2013). However, in project management, there is also a need for the team to understand the long-term goal of the business so that they know how they have contributed to it and learn how they can make an impact. Project success depends on effective communication and this is the importance of communication in any project. Improving communication maximizes success and minimizes risk. In addition, if a project manager can develop effective communication with its stakeholder; this may mean more projects for him and the team.

According to Baker (2017), the mode of Project communication has an effect on commitment of individual team members handling construction projects in Mogadishu-Somalia. Yammarino and Naughton (2008) demonstrated that a positive relationship exists between amount of time spent communicating and the level of effort expended by each project team member on execution of tasks. Similar findings have been reported by Ng *et al.*, (2016). Effective project communication creates a feeling of responsibility and attachment between a stakeholder and the project tasks that makes him/her indebted to the project thereby creating an atmosphere for individual team members to act without much control and coercion. Under search circumstances, what drives a person to work is the emotional attachment to the project as natured by communication. This is consistent with Fishbein and Ajzen's (2015) findings that workers with positive attitude about the task carry out certain role behaviors well beyond the basic minimum levels required of them. They for example may not take extra breaks and they tend to obey the project rules and regulations even

when no one is watching, they attend meetings that are not mandatory (Steers, 1997), but considered important.

According to Jeon, (2012), states that knowledge in any organization is shared both formally and informally between the workforce of any organization and they communicate socially. According to Kim, (2013) informal learning is also dependent upon the general interests and it is thought to be “caught not taught”. As mentoring is the process in which a person provides and shares his knowledge, skills and experience to the one with less experience and knowledge, so there is an interpersonal relationship between the two. Contu, (2013) Self-Directed Learning is also a sub part of informal learning in which an individual makes himself prepared to learn from his own. It creates spiritual development in a person. In this form of learning, a person knows how to do a certain task, or how to react in a particular situation. In self-directed learning, the learner is fully responsible for his or her choosing a course of action to plan, to carry out and to evaluate these learning experiences.

According to Coopey, (2010), He also notices that it is not necessary that people learn alone, but the thing is that people learn when they are in relationship with other people on their work, on their leisure time and their time at home. People who are independent learners according to Dirx, (2019) are not intended to learn by their own. In an extension to this concept, he finds out that hobbyists do not learn alone. He also notices and finds out that we people are aware of the fact that mostly we learn in collaborations with others in Self Directed Learning. This self-directed learning results the self-development of individuals.

2.2.3 Influence of Communication Channels on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu –Somalia

As described previously, communication is the exchange of information between different parties (Lefaix-Durand & Kozak, 2019). This interchange of information naturally requires channels to go through in order to be delivered from one person to another. These channels are called communication channels. There are various types of communication channels that people use when exchanging information. Some common channels are e-mails, telephone calls, meetings (Tenhiälä & Salvador, 2014), face-to-face conversations, video conferencing, web-based tools, bulletins, documents and memos (Oke & Idiagbon-Oke, 2010). It is further explained that face-to-

face, videoconferencing, telephone calls and e-mails carry a greater realistic feeling of actual physical presence of the person communicating information (Oke & Idiagbon-Oke, 2010). The choice of communication channels however depends on the nature or characteristics of a task. It means that channels are more appropriate in some situations and less appropriate in others. Furthermore, the more appropriate a channel is to the nature of the task, the more effective the information will be communicated. The information itself will also be less ambiguous if delivered through a suitable channel (Oke & Idiagbon-Oke, 2010). This is important in order to avoid misunderstandings. On the other hand, other existing research explains how workers in organizations sometimes use combinations of communication channels, either at the same time or in a sequence, in order to complete an exchange of information to another party. It is suggested that employees do this because of norms or routines within various organizations (Watson-Manheim & Bélanger, 2017).

Umeå (2014), project office give due emphasis for the role of communication Informal and formal, the basic communication channels identified in the study are; meetings (physical), mail correspondence, non-verbal communication like logos of the project, share point and informal communication interaction in the project organization. Besides, the role of the glass house identified as a big means of communication tools to different tourists and public at large.

Furthermore, “informal communication can be work by different communication channels. Some of the channels that we use in the internal communication process are: email, telephone communication, daily physical communication and meeting every Monday that aims to evaluate the activities that has been done by the project” (Umeå, 2014).

As explained earlier, informal communication can be accomplished through various means of channels. What has been found in a research on chief executive officers (CEOs) is that most CEOs commonly use email, but also face-to-face channels by talking and managing through direct contact with their employees. The findings also show that the usage of intranet and print media such as magazines, newsletters, posters, memos, and fliers are both popular and important tools in internal communication. Other, but less commonly used tools are teleconferencing and streamline video/audio (Men, 2015).

It is shown that employees prefer face-to-face communication by their managers due to of its nature of immediate feedback and management's ability to directly listen and respond (Men, 2014). The finding that employees prefer having discussion forums and direct meetings with their managers strengthens this (Friedl & Vercic, 2010). Also, this same study shows that information that is considered strategic was preferably received by traditional channels such as e-mail newsletters, intranet news and employee meetings. Conversely, and despite social media's vast usage in the employees' private lives, workers still prefer to use the intranet news feed instead of social media when receiving general organizational information. Furthermore, social networking for the sharing of intranet news is preferred over employee magazines. Likewise is employee discussion forums preferred over any type of media when the discussion is centered around issues concerning themselves (Friedl & Vercic, 2010).

During a project, communication can occur in various directions depending on who is communicating. There is upward communication to management from your own organization and the customer's organization. Lateral communication takes place with customers and within project teams. Machinery needs to be put in place for further communication to take place, either downward communication (from superior to sub-ordinate), horizontal communication (between colleagues) or upward communication (from sub-ordinates to superior). Mehra (2019) stated that communication will always involve more than one person.

Figure 2.1: Showing the three communication channels of the project manager

Source: Adopted from Keyton, (2011)

Building and measuring effectiveness communication channels in a project starts when the scope is defined during Planning phase (Scope Management Plan, Scope Statement, and the Work Breakdown Structure-WBS). Scope is built around goals and end-deliverables the customer or

sponsor needs. A solid Scope Change procedure is compiled during the Scope Planning process. Through this procedure scope of project is kept under control throughout the entire lifecycle (Ahadzie, 2015). At the end of each phase, and before moving to the next phase, the PM verifies the deliverables of the phase against the scope baseline to check whether the agreed upon scope is being met and to verify that the project in total is still appropriate and in line with the overall strategies of the company or the customer (Ankrah, 2012). As a result of this continuous control over scope corrective and preventive actions are taken to keep the project focused on the original plan or to update the plan itself to cope with the ultimate goals pursued by the customer or the sponsor.

Communication channels clarifies project tasks, creates teamwork and gets all stakeholders involved in the running of the project (Ssenyange 2011). Maintaining effective communication with the project team over time raises the quantity of social ties amongst the different stakeholders, (Nangoli and Ahimbisibwe, 2012). Although not always a key focus for most project managers, communication is needed especially in the early stages of most projects as an interaction pattern among project members, to establish understanding, trust, build coordination and support from a variety of project personnel (Nangoli & Ahimbisibwe, 2012, Zhong & Low's 2019, Van Vuuren *et al*, 2016). Despite the issue of project communication being key in fostering project success, around 80% of projects embarked on in most institutions of higher learning in Uganda have not lived to their expectations.

For any organisation to change its focus and become more competitive (Atkin *et al.*, 2013). Project communication is a key driver to improving quality of services while its absence or use of inappropriate means can act as a barrier to change and may lead to deterioration of the accounting function. Organisations which do not have performance means in their processes, procedures, and plans experience lower performance and higher customer dissatisfaction and employee turnover (Atkins, 2014). Measuring the performance of the accounting department yields benefits to organisations such as quality of output, enhanced profitability, assured supplies, quality improvements and competitive advantage as was noted by (Atkinson, 2012).

With studies proving that the core of project communication is the individuals plus their personal capacity to communicate, this brings in a new dimension of training staffs in communication

channel skills. Herkt (2017) argues that the core difference between very successful projects and less successful projects is in the ability of project manager's development of interpersonal skills. A project manager's major responsibility should be executing decision making and building efficient mutual relationships among a diverse group of project stakeholders (Herkt, 2017; Parkin, 2017). In agreement Schein (2016) insists that its only through communication that information is shared to provide a fundamental understanding of the tasks that are to be performed as well as the goals to shot at, since most project are always undertaken by people from various ethnic complexities and attitudes. Ng *et al.*, (2016) adds that effectual communication creates a feeling of responsibility within a person and the tasks he has been allocated to accomplish, making it possible for members and various stakeholders on the team to act without much supervisory control.

This tool is viewed as the most comprehensive in trying to measure all aspects of communication channels in an organization (Hargie & Tourish, 2010). It covers the researcher's scope in project communication extensively, with a total of 122 questions covered within the 8 sections of the questionnaire, addressing issue relating to amount, of information, timelines of information, communication relationship, follow up and satisfaction with the level of outcome. Several researchers have been credited the tool with interesting features like being able to compare actual and ideal situation, having both face validity and predictive validity, and being very comprehensive in all aspects (ICAC, 2010, Nangoli, 2010, wilihnganz, 1988). With a number of studies adopting this tool extensively, for example Downs & Adrian, (2014) used it in weighing to employee perceptions of their organization internal communication practices, Wulandari, (2010) used in measuring the relations that exist between trust communication, and employee satisfaction, it has certainly proved to be an efficient tool in measuring project communication.

Additional Varona, (2016) contends that communication channels drives people to work and collaborate with each other to achieve asset targets. Since projects involve people of different qualities and desires, the greater the level of communication in a project the higher the level of teamwork and performance of projects. Basing from this discussion its evident that communication positively impacts on project performance and eventual success; it's upon this that we want to assess whether the registered failures in public universities project can be attributed to failure in communication.

2.2.4 Relationship between project communication and performance

Reviewing the works of Crown (2010), Westring (2017), and Anvuur and Kumaraswamy (2016), the performance of the construction industry in Somalia is poor and saddled with several problems ranging from contract administration, through complex and lengthy payment procedure, delayed payments to that of project execution. It is noteworthy that clients' delay in payment to service providers (contractor and practitioners) also affects payments of salaries and wages of their staff. This is because sometimes these delays run into several months and thus, these employers find it difficult to continue paying their staff.

The unskilled labours of the contractors form the largest group and the lack of guaranteed income, despite their commitment to work, shows an unpleasant side of the industry that is seen as one of the largest employer of labour. Due to the representation of construction workers in the working population of the country, such situation reflects on the socio-economic life of ordinary Somalis. The reverse is also true. This could be likened to a period of freeze on government projects. To some extent, in Somalia, there are practical reasons to subscribe to the argument that construction industry is a regulator of the economy Ashworth (2014).

The construction site is the place where the efforts made by the design team in visualizing the client's requirements will be put into practice and the client's dream made a reality. Generally, site meetings are the regular meetings held on site to discuss the progress of the project to date, the difficulties and delays arising from the project at hand. According to Bansard *et al.*, (2013), communication on site between the parties can be greatly improved with the aid of site meetings. All the relevant parties like the architect, contract manager, general foreman, clerk of works, main subcontractors, etc could be in attendance. Other methods of communication on site include weekly reports, which are a complete record summarizing daily happenings on site for the week and recorded by the clerk of works.

2.3 Related Literature

On nearly every job, certain difficulties arise, usually practical difficulties in construction to certain detailed drawing. These problems in many cases could have been overcome had there been consultation between the architect and builder at an earlier stage (Baker *et al.*, 2013). Builders are seldom aware of many such problems until the job has progressed considerably, because of the usual procedure of issuing detailed drawings long after the project has started. This point alone

raises communication problems, in that the builder may have to order purpose made component, and the project could be delayed during their manufacture (Banner and Gagne, 2015). On the other hand, many builders cause a lot of delays. There are many situations where it is obvious to the builder or site agent that he is going to have to seek the architect's advice or ask for details about certain points, but it is not mentioned until such a late stage that delay occurs.

Within a building company, the type of communication system and the speed with which it works are to a large extent a function of the size of the organisation (Bansard *et al.*, 2013). The smaller the company, the faster information will be disseminated. With large companies, a communication network has to be developed that ensure that the information necessary for decision-making gets to where it may be wanted. This can sometimes lead to overload "in" trays with the majority of the information being irrelevant to the particular department.

Communication according to Beatham *et al.*, (2014), is said to be effective within the working group in the construction industry only when the transmitted ideas achieve their desired action or reaction, as the operations involve the team effort of the client, quantity surveyor, architect, consulting engineer, specialists and the contractor's organization with the main objective of getting things done through human beings. Belassi and Tukul, (2016) noted that to better understand the concept of communication in the construction industry, it is important to acknowledge the roles, responsibilities and the authority of various participants on a typical construction project and how information gets exchanged.

External communication in projects means the communication between the project and its relevant environment, typically the client and end-user organisation (Bernard, 2012). Management of the functional organisation is important for a project in order to achieve and maintain the organisational commitment. It is not so exceptional for the functional organisations to have resistive forces that don't support the project. Often resistance and negative attitudes are a result of the lack of information. People simply don't know why the project has been founded and where it is aiming. To create a positive profile for itself a project should keep the stakeholders well informed on its goals and operations. Insufficient communication creates a news vacuum that will be filled with rumours (Bissah *et al.*, 2013).

Internal communication has two emphases in a project: the steering committee and the project team. A steering committee is the top decision making forum in a project. Its task is to control and support the project manager. Interpersonal information exchange between the project and the client organisation and also the end-user organisation takes place in the steering committee. Although the majority of the official decision making takes place in the steering committee, the cooperation between the project manager and the steering committee should not be limited only to the meetings (Bosch and Philips, 2013). By also keeping contact to the steering committees key members between meetings, a project manager can ensure that steering committee is up-to-date on the project's performance and that the decision making mechanism will progress smoothly when it is needed. Within the project group effective communication is based on the key factor of the project leadership: manage by walking and talking.

2.5 Gaps in the Literature

Most of the existing literature does not specifically show how project communication influences the success of projects in organisations. The research by Claire, (2011) is applicable in the commercial sector which are mainly profit oriented projects. Project communication in Non-Governmental organisations and projects usually takes a different course in their execution because they exist for other reasons other than for commercial ones.

A study conducted by Robbins, (2013) revealed that wages and salaries are recognized to be a significant, but complex, multidimensional predictor of job satisfaction hence enhancing project performance. However, this study did not indicate the reason why some project staff choose not to perform better at the project despite having paid those wages and salaries.

Another study conducted by Engwall, (2014) indicated that communication plays an integral role in keeping a project on task. The specifics of communication, including the method and frequency, vary depending on your project's needs. However, this study did not reveal how different forms of communication such as formal and informal communication can significantly impact on the performance of the projects, of which this study intends to close these gaps identified above.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

This chapter dealt with the methods and procedures that were used in sample selection, data collection, analysis and presentation. It includes; sampling techniques, data collection methods, study population, sampling procedure and sample size, data analysis methods, research instruments, ethical consideration and anticipated limitations of the study.

3.1 Research Design

This study employed a cross-sectional research design. Cross-sectional research design is a type of observational study that analyzes data from a population, or a representative subset, at a specific point in time. Both quantitative and qualitative approaches were used in data collection. Quantitative approach involved use of a questionnaire. Qualitative approach involved use of interview guide. The researcher used this type of research design because it is less costly to perform and does not require a lot of time.

3.2 Population of the Study

According to UNDP (2018) Report, the Digfer general teaching hospital construction has a total population of 149 project staff and these include; 15 top authorities of the Project, 117 Project staff (Casual labourers), 10 Project coordinators and 4 Project supervisors and 02 project managers and therefore the target population was 149 respondents. The reason for selecting these categories of respondents is due to the fact that the researcher expects them to have a very good understanding of the Project communication and project performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu.

3.3 Study Area

3.4 Sample Size Determination

Out of the target population of 149, a sample size of 109 was selected, by using Slovene's formula. The sample is sufficiently high and representative enough to validate the findings.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

Where n = minimum sample size

N = target population

e = level of significance (0.05)

Therefore:

$$n = \frac{149}{1 + 149(0.05^2)}$$

$$n = \frac{149}{1 + 149 \times 0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{149}{1 + 0.3725} = 108.56$$

Therefore n = 109 respondents

The table below gives a selected population from their respective organization and employees.

Table 3.1: Population and Sample Size Summary

Category of respondents	Target population	Sample size	Sampling procedure
Top authorities of the Project (Directors)	15	10	Purposive sampling
Project staff (Casual labourers)	117	87	Systematic Random sampling
Project coordinators	11	08	Random sampling
Project supervisors	04	03	Purposive sampling
Project managers	02	01	Purposive sampling
Total	149	109	

Source: UNDP (2018)

3.5 Sampling Procedure

The sampling technique that was used in this study is systematic random sampling. Using this method, a list of the employees in the organization was compiled. In selecting the respondents,

two consecutive respondents were selected while skipping the next one respondent and selecting the next two all over again until the sample size is met. This sampling technique was employed because it is simple and prevents cases of bias in sampling. Purposive sampling was also used to determine high profile respondents like the top authorities of the Project and Project supervisors who were believed to have more information about the topic under study.

3.6 Data Collection Instruments

The researcher used two instruments in this study which are questionnaire and interview.

3.7 Data collection procedure

3.7.1 Self-administered questionnaire

The questionnaire was the main primary source of data collection and thus was of great relevance to the researcher as they tend to offer a quick way to get results and also helped me to gather information from a large audience of respondents including; Project staff (Casual labourers), Project coordinators and Project supervisors. The identified sample was served with the questionnaire directly by the researcher. To obtain quantitative data, one set of questionnaire was used for all respondents. The questionnaire also aims at getting responses from the respondents about their views on project communication and project performance. In addition to this Self-administered questionnaire are preferred because they are relatively easy to analyze and a large number of people in Mogadishu can be reached relatively easily.

3.7.2 Interviews

Interview means face to face interaction between the interviewee and the interviewer. The interviews were held with the Top authorities of the Project identified as they were purposively crucial in providing explanations to the topic under study.

The questions for the interview were both open-ended and closed. The open-ended questions gave chance to more discussions, while the closed ended questions were asked for particular responses. The interview method helped to collect additional views from respondents on the theme of the study. The questions were filled on spot and the respondents were interviewed from their offices to save time. This method allowed further probing and clarification of questions that tended to be difficult and not clear to the respondents. It also enhanced responses for

questions which was regarded as sensitive.

3.8 Data Analysis Procedure

3.8.1 Quantitative data analysis

The quantitative data involved information from the questionnaires only. Data from the field was too raw for proper interpretation. It was therefore vital to put it into order and structure it, so as to drive meaning and information from it. The raw data obtained from questionnaires was cleaned, sorted and coded. The coded data was entered into the computer, checked and statistically analyzed using the statistical package for social scientists (SPSS) software package to generate descriptive and inferential statistics.

However, extent of project communication and project Performance was established through basic descriptive statistics such as means. Further still, significant difference and significant relationship between the two study variables will be determined by the Pearson's Linear Correlation Coefficient at 0.05 level of significance and regression model analysis. Data on effectiveness in project communication and project performance was interpreted. However, qualitative data was acquired from interview schedules with the respondents.

3.8.2 Qualitative data analysis

Qualitative data was analyzed using manual coding on the transcripts to identify the significant statements across individual interviews. Subsequent readings of the significant statements helped in identifying meaning of units or sub-themes emerging within the patterns. For presentation of thematic findings, both textural and structural descriptions were used in the results section. Textural descriptions are significant statements used to write what the participants experienced. Structural descriptions are the interpretation of the context or setting that influenced participants' experiences. For textural descriptions, the quotes of participants were given in italics with the respondent to whom that quote belongs marked with type. The structural descriptions was interpreted by the researcher and provided in plain text.

3.9 Inclusion/exclusion criteria

Inclusion and exclusion criteria define who can be included or excluded from the study sample. The inclusion criteria identify the study population in a consistent, reliable, uniform and objective manner. The research study will be conducted at Digfer general teaching hospital and the population target aged of the study will be between the ages of 20 and 41 and respondents will have experience between 1 to 5 years' experience. The exclusion criteria include factors or characteristics that make the recruited population ineligible for the study. An exclusion criterion for this study might be people who don't have any certificate will not be included or doesn't involve anything for this project. If the respondents become 41 years will disqualify for the study. Employees who are less experienced will be excluded because they will have impact to the outcome.

3.10 Quality Control

3.10.1 Validity

Validity of the instrument was ensured through expert judgment and the researcher made sure the coefficient of validity to be at least 70%. The researcher consulted his supervisor for expert knowledge on questionnaire construction. After the assessment of the questionnaire, the necessary adjustments were made bearing in mind of the objectives of the study. The formula that was used to calculate the validity of the instrument is:-

$$CVI = \frac{\text{no of items declared valid}}{\text{total no of items}}$$

3.10.2 Reliability

Reliability is a measure of the degree to which a research instrument yields consistent results or data after repeated trials (Muganda & Mugenda, 2003). Reliability of the instrument was established through a test-retest technique. The researcher conducted a pre-test of the instrument on a group of subjects and waits for one week then administer the same test to the same subjects in the second time.

Cronbach's alpha was also used to determine the reliability of the instruments. A Cronbach's alpha value of 0.70 and above is considered to be the criteria for demonstrating internal consistency of new scale and established scales respectively.

The table below shows each main constructs of the model was considered acceptable since the Cronbach's alpha related to each of them exceeded 0.70, confirming satisfactory reliability.

3.11 Ethical Considerations

To ensure confidentiality of the information provided by the respondents and to ascertain the practice of ethics in this study, the following activities were implemented by the researcher: all questionnaires were coded to provide anonymity of respondents responses, solicit permission through a written request to the concerned officials of the organizations included in the study, respondents were requested to sign the Informed Consent Form, no respondents were threatened or coerced to participate, authors quoted were fully recognized through citation and referencing and present the findings in a generalized manner.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS / FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the data collected from primary sources as well as the analysis, interpretation and discussion of findings, with reference to study objectives and related literature.

4.1 Response Rate

The study targeted a sample of 109 respondents. However, out of 109 questionnaires distributed 104 respondents completely filled in and returned the questionnaires, this represented a 95% response rate. This is a reliable response rate for analysis as Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) showed that 50% of response rate is sufficient for analysis and presentation of the data, 60% is reliable and 70% of response rate and over is excellent. However, 5% of the respondents were reluctant to fill the questionnaire this was due to reasons like, the respondent were not available to fill them in at the required time and even after subsequent follow-up there were no positive reactions from them.

Table 4.1: Response Rate

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Filled in questionnaires	104	95
Non response	5	5
Total	109	100%

Source: Primary Data, 2019

4.2 Demographic characteristics of respondents

The study aimed at establishing the general information about the respondents. The study used this information to base the study finding on the experience of the respondents and familiarity of the respondent to the information that the study sought.

4.2.1 Gender

Gender of the respondents was collected to establish the composition of the respondents as regards to the two sex of male and female and the findings are presented in table 4.2 below.

Table.4.2: Showing sex of respondents

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Male	76	70%
Female	33	30%
Total	109	100%

Source: Primary Data, 2019

Further the study aimed at establishing the distribution of respondents' gender. According to the study findings most (70%) of the respondents were male while the rest 30% were female. This implies that majority of most of the employees in regulatory bodies are male while their counterpart occupies only small portion.

4.2.2 Age category of respondents

The respondents were told during the study to indicate the age bracket where they belong and the findings are presented in table 4.3 below;

Table 4.3: Age of respondents

Category	Frequency	Percentage
20-25	48	44%
26-30	30	28%
31-36	18	17%
41 and above	13	12%
Total	109	100%

Source: Primary Data, 2019

The findings from table 4.3 above shows that most of the respondents 48(44%) were aged between the 20-25 years, followed by 30(28%) who were aged between 26-30 years, 18(17%) were between 31 and 36 years, and the least proportion of respondents 13(12%) were 41 years and above. This implies that the Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu - Somalia is mainly composed of middle aged adults since they are believed to be energetic and strong enough to operate the project.

4.2.3 Marital Status

Data was collected from the respondents about their marital status which was in the types of the married, single, widow and divorced.

Table 4.4: Showing marital status

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Single	70	64%
Married	20	18%
Widow	10	9%
Divorced	9	8%
Total	109	100

Source: Primary Data, 2019

The findings from Table 4.4 shows that out of the 109 respondents, 70(64%) of the respondents reported being single, 20(18%) reported being married, 10(9%) reported being Widow, 9(8)% were divorced. The findings inculcated that all the categories of the respondents were all covered in regard to their Marital Status and the majority of the respondents were Single because they secured the highest percentage (64%). Hence implying that the respondents in Digfer teaching hospital construction project are mainly single.

4.2.4 Education level of respondents

During the interviews, the respondents were also told to indicate their level of education as presented in table 4.5 below;

Table 4.5: Education level of respondents

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Certificates	15	14%
Diploma	28	26%
Bachelors	44	40%
Masters	22	20%
Total	109	100

Source: Primary Data, 2019

Table 4.5 above presents the findings on the level of education of the respondents that participated in the study. Results indicate that majority of the respondents 44(40%) had acquired Bachelors degrees of education, followed by 28(26%) who were Diploma holders, 22(20%) were Masters Holders, 15(14%) were certificates holders. The results imply that the Digfer general teaching

hospital construction in Mogadishu - Somalia was dominated by people who are Bachelors holders. The results further confirm that the project was composed of people with vast knowledge and this contributed significantly to the study findings.

4.2.4 Working experience

The distribution of the respondents by their job occupation is indicated in table 4.6.

Table 4.6: Working experience

Categories	Frequency	Percentage
0- 1 year	27	25%
2-3 years	30	28%
4-6 years	38	35%
5 years and above	14	13%
Total	109	100

Source: Primary Data, 2019

In table 4.6, in terms of years spent working, majority of the respondents (35%) had worked for 4-6 years, followed by those between 2-3 years (28%), 25% had worked for 0-1 year, finally 13% had worked for 5 years and above. This indicated that majority of these respondents had enough experience in their fields, and therefore they could provide the researcher with the information required.

4.3 Description of independent variable: Project Communication (n=109)

This section presents the description of the independent variable using means and standard deviation. According to the conceptual framework (Figure 2.1), the Independent variable in this study was based on the study objectives in terms of 3 constructs (i.e. Formal communication, Informal communication and Communication channels) among employees in Digfer general teaching hospital construction. Thus section B of the questionnaires was devoted to the Independent variable.

4.3.1. Findings on the effect of Formal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu -Somalia

Objective number one of the study was to examine effect of Formal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu -Somalia. Several

questions were asked in this regard. The responses are in respect of this question as shown below:

Table 4.7: Showing Responses about the effect of Formal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu -Somalia.

Response	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
The project manager's major responsibility is to build supportive social networks (collaborative relationships) among a diverse group of stakeholders.	109	3.35	1.830	Very Good
Successful project management and formal communication is about being there for everyone, being in touch with the real challenges of the project, understanding the real issues within the team who must work on the the project	109	3.05	1.746	Good
Formal Communication must circulate through the project management teams of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu, and external stakeholders to maintain the health and the viability of the project	109	2.78	1.667	Good
Project managers handling the Digfer general teaching hospital construction In Mogadishu should be mindful of any cultural differences among team members and other stakeholders that could result in miscommunication.	109	2.46	1.568	Poor
Formal Communication plays an integral role in keeping a project on task	109	3.27	1.288	Very Good
Project communication acts as a connecting factor that links the various stakeholders of the projects like the Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu	109	2.84	1.54	Good
The project manager is charged with guiding all aspects of the project, including the formal communication plan	109	2.75	1.46	Good
Formal Communication may mean being able to talk, speak and be listened to.	109	3.27	1.808	Very Good
Average Mean		2.97		Good

Source: Primary Data 2019

The following mean ranges were used to arrive at the mean of the individual indicators and interpretation:

For the effect between Formal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu -Somalia.

Mean Range	Response Mode	Interpretation
3.26-4.00	Strongly agree	Very good
2.51-3.25	Agree	Good
1.76-2.50	Disagree	Poor
1.00-1.75	Strongly disagree	Very poor

Results in table 4.7 indicated that the effect between Formal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu -Somalia was rated good and this was indicated by the overall mean of 2.97, implying that there is a formalized system intended to help the Digfer general teaching hospital construction on how plans are drawn after consulting the members. And the project manager's major responsibility is to build supportive social networks (collaborative relationships) among a diverse group of stakeholders and this was indicated by the average mean of 3.35, implying that the Digfer general teaching hospital construction managers major responsibility is to build supportive social networks. Successful project management and formal communication is about being there for everyone, being in touch with the real challenges of the project, understanding the real issues within the team who must work on the project this was indicated by the average mean of 3.05 this further shows that Successful project management with formal communication is about being there for everyone involved in the project.

Still results in table 4.7 indicated that Formal Communication must circulate through the project management teams of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu, and external stakeholders to maintain the health and the viability of the project, this was rated good with an average mean of 2.78, this implies that the Digfer general teaching hospital construction Formal Communication circulates through the project management teams which is helpful to the way of increasing its effectiveness.

Results indicated that Project managers handling the Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu should be mindful of any cultural differences among team members and other stakeholders that could result in miscommunication and this was rated poor (mean=2.46), this

therefore implies that Project managers handling the Digfer general teaching hospital construction are not mindful of any cultural differences among team members and other stakeholders that could result in miscommunication.

Results however indicated that Formal Communication plays an integral role in keeping a project on task and this was rated very good (mean=3.27), this implies that Formal Communication plays an integral role in keeping a project on task by respondents of selected Digfer general teaching hospital construction operating in Mogadishu, Somalia capital.

Results indicated that project communication acts as a connecting factor that links the various stakeholders of the projects like the Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu, this was rated Good by the average mean of 2.84, hence implying that project communication acts as a connecting factor linking various stakeholders of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu thus increasing on the effectiveness of the Digfer general teaching hospital construction.

Results however indicated that the project manager is charged with guiding all aspects of the project, including the formal communication plan and this was rated Good (mean=2.75), this implies that the project manager is charged with guiding all aspects of the project, including the formal communication plan. Thus most of the respondents were of the view to the statement support of the project.

Results indicated that Formal Communication may mean being able to talk, speak and be listened to, this was rated very good by the average mean of 3.75, hence implying that the respondents all agreed that formal Communication may mean being able to talk, speak and be listened to thus their knowledge gives an ideal effectiveness on the Digfer general teaching hospital construction.

Interview responses;

Regarding formal communication towards performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu –Somalia, According to one of the Project Supervisor said that....,

“...Since everyone has their own views on the project of Digfer general teaching hospital construction culture of capital, these ideas are facts that everyone

needs to share and experience on it. The expectation of the project office is to let people understand about the objective of the program that can be achieved by sharing ideas in different ways”.

More so according to one of the project coordinator she said that;

“Formal communication can be work by different communication channels. Some of the channels that we use in the formal communication process are: email, telephone communication, daily physical communication and meeting every Monday that aims to evaluate the activities that has been done by the project”.

More so according to one of the project manager he said that;

“We communicate by weekly meeting, telephone interview from Stockholm and Malmö who coordinates the communication process, meeting every Monday morning , email communication and finally we try to have from 2-3 weeks every year free from external meeting so, that we can discuss and communicate only internally”.

4.3.2 Effect of Informal Communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu -Somalia.

Objective number two of the study was to establish the effects of Informal Communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu -Somalia. Several questions were asked and the responses are summarized, analyzed and interpreted below:

Table 4.8: Shows the Effect of Informal Communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu -Somalia

RESPONSE	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Informal Communication has clarified project tasks, created teamwork and got all stakeholders involved in the running of the Digfer general teaching hospital construction	109	3.27	1.808	Very Good
Informal communication effects working with our supervisors so as to perform more in our duties.	109	3.21	1.792	Good
Informal communication has to a very large extent been used to determine our level of performance at work in the company.	109	2.82	1.679	Good

Informal Communication has increased the level of commitment of workers in an organization, and this may be the case under normal circumstances	109	2.18	1.476	Poor
Informal Communication has imposed increased responsibilities that have made our construction job more valuable and important.	109	2.87	1.694	Good
Construction staff with more work experience have more respect for their jobs, can apply their experience to their jobs, and are skilled and successful in doing their jobs	109	2.99	1.54	Good
Informal Communication has provided technical support and guidance to project staff of Digfer general teaching hospital construction	109	2.82	1.679	Good
Informal Communication is recognized to be a significant, but complex, multidimensional predictor of job satisfaction in Digfer general teaching hospital constructions	109	2.18	1.476	Poor
Average Mean		2.79	1.49	Good

Source: Primary Data, 2019

The following mean ranges were used to arrive at the mean of the individual indicators and interpretation:

For the Effect of Informal Communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu -Somalia.

Mean Range	Response Mode	Interpretation
3.26-4.00	Strongly agree	Very good
2.51-3.25	Agree	Good
1.76-2.50	Disagree	Poor
1.00-1.75	Strongly disagree	Very poor

From table 4.8 with respect to the effect of Informal Communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu -Somalia, this rated good and this was indicated by the average mean of 2.79, hence implying that Informal Communication is carried out and always assessed well in order to improve project effectiveness. Informal Communication has clarified project tasks, created teamwork and got all stakeholders involved in the running of the Digfer general teaching hospital construction (mean=3.27), this was rated very good implying that Informal Communication has clarified project tasks, created teamwork and got all stakeholders involved in the running of the Project. Informal communication effects working with our supervisors so as to perform more in our duties (mean=3.21), this was rated good thus this implies

that Informal communication effects working with our supervisors so as to perform more in our duties hence leading to effectiveness of project communication in projects, more so this means that the use of informal communication in the project still continues to be a very essential aspect of the project.

Informal communication has to a very large extent been used to determine our level of performance at work in the company and this was rated good by the average mean of 2.82, thus this indicates that Informal communication has to a very large extent been used to determine the level of performance at work in the company, thus implying that most project managers operating in different projects in Mogadishu have relied on informal communication to help them in the effective running of the project.

However the results also shown that Informal Communication has increased the level of commitment of workers in an organization, and this may be the case under normal circumstances and was rated poor with a mean of 2.18 and this indicated that respondents don't agree that Informal Communication has increased the level of commitment of workers in an organization, and this may be the case under normal circumstances hence declining in the level of commitment of workers in construction projects.

More so for the issue of Informal Communication has imposed increased responsibilities that have made our construction job more valuable and important, this was rated good by the average mean of 2.87, this implies that Informal Communication has imposed increased responsibilities that have made the construction job more valuable and important in Mogadishu.

Furthermore from the results it showed that Construction staffs with more work experience have more respect for their jobs, can apply their experience to their jobs, and are skilled and successful in doing their jobs with a mean (2.99) and this was rated Good, hence implying that Construction staffs with more work experience have more respect for their jobs thus a significant effectiveness towards project performance.

Informal Communication has provided technical support and guidance to project staff of Digfer general teaching hospital construction with a mean (2.82) and this was rated good implying that Informal Communication has provided technical support and guidance to project staff.

Lastly, the results above indicated that Informal Communication is recognized to be significant, but complex, multidimensional predictor of job satisfaction in Digfer general teaching hospital constructions with a mean (2.18) and this was rated poor hence implying that the respondents didn't agree that Informal Communication is recognized to be significant, but complex, multidimensional predictor of job satisfaction in Digfer general teaching hospital construction.

Interview Response

Regarding a more understanding on the informal communication towards performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu –Somalia, According to one of the Project Manager said that,

“We have to solve the problems of the society when we say that, we will support all the stakeholders who wants to do a job. Informal communication creates common attitude towards something, I believe the communication within the office is big since we are very big organization”.

More so another staff member said that:

“ ..To keep up the pace and to work with the idea of co-creation and a level of participation from team members, so that everyone can communicate in the project”. We believe communication plays a key role internally and externally to speed-up our day-to-day activities.

Another staff member replied about informal communication he said:

“We try to facilitate the flow of internal communication in the office among employees. The way we organized the office is simple for everyone can hear and be part of the discussion. For example, when I talk by telephone everyone can hear and take part of the discussion, since we don't have private rooms and vice-versa”.

4.3.3 Findings on the influence of communication channels on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu

Objective number three of the study was to examine the influence of communication channels on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu. The responses in this area are presented, analyzed and discussed below:

Table 4.9: Response on the influence of communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu

Response	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Communication channels in Digfer general teaching hospital construction means the communication between the project and its relevant environment, typically the client and end-user	109	3.27	1.808	Very Good
Communication channels are effective within the working group in the construction industry in Somalia	109	3.21	1.792	Good
Communication channels within the Digfer general teaching hospital construction group is effective based on the key factors like; Past experiences, Education and Intellectual difference	109	2.93	1.711	Good
Project communication channel management is vital to the success of construction of projects	109	2.18	1.476	Poor
The operations in Digfer general teaching hospital construction involve the team effort of clients, quantity surveyor, architect, consulting engineer and project specialists is strengthened by the communication channels	109	2.87	1.694	Good
Communication channels plans and strategies must be determined /established at the outset	109	3.10	1.761	Good
Average Mean		2.93		Good

Source: Primary Data, 2019

The following mean ranges were used to interpret the means:

For the influence of communication channels on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu

Mean Range	Response Mode	Interpretation
3.26-4.00	Strongly agree	Very good
2.51-3.25	Agree	Good

1.76-2.50	Disagree	Poor
1.00-1.75	Strongly disagree	Very poor

From table 4.9 with respect to the influence of communication channels on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu, this was rated good and this was indicated by the overall average mean of 2.93, hence implying that communication channels are used effectively for the good performance of the project hence leading to the effectiveness of its activities. Results in table 4.9 indicated that Communication channels in Digfer general teaching hospital construction means the communication between the project and its relevant environment, typically to the client and end-user and this was rated very good and indicated by the mean of 3.27, which implies that Communication channels in Digfer general teaching hospital construction is the communication between the project and its relevant environment, typically the client and end-user. And this becomes an advantage to the management of Digfer when communicating to the end users and clients.

Results further indicated that Communication channels are effective within the working group in the construction industry in Somalia and this was rated good (mean=3.21), this implied that Communication channels being effective within the working group in the construction industry in Somalia hence making projects more effective and a success.

More so Communication channels within the Digfer general teaching hospital construction group is effective based on the key factors like; Past experiences, Education and Intellectual difference was ranked as good (mean=2.93), however this indicates that since Communication channels within the Digfer general teaching hospital construction group is effective based on the key factors like; Past experiences, Education and Intellectual difference within the project hence leading to better performance of the construction project.

Results further indicated that Project communication channel management is vital to the success of construction of projects was rated poor (mean=2.18), however this implies that the respondents didn't agree that Project communication channel management is vital to the success of construction of projects.

More so the operations in Digfer general teaching hospital construction involve the team effort of clients, quantity surveyor, architect, consulting engineer and project specialists is strengthened by the communication channels and was rated good as (mean=2.87), this showed that effective operations in Digfer general teaching hospital construction involve the team effort of clients, quantity surveyor, architect, consulting engineer and project specialists is strengthened by the communication channels.

Results further indicated that Communication channels plans and strategies must be determined /established at the outset was rated good (mean=3.10), however this implies that Communication channels plans and strategies must be determined /established at the outset has led on the effectiveness of construction of the project in Mogadishu Somalia.

Interview Response

Regarding a more understanding on the communication channels influence towards performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu –Somalia, According to one of the Project Manager said that,

“ ..To keep up the pace and to work with the idea of co-creation and a level of participation from team members, so that everyone can communicate in the project”. We believe communication channels play a key role internally and externally to speed-up our day-to-day activities.

Furthermore, one of the project managers interviewed agreed that....

"He was aware of role of communication channels in performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction. He further mentioned that through these communication channels, stakeholders feel ownership of projects and solutions and encourage transparency and accountability of the organizations offering service".

4.3.4 Findings on the relationship between project communication and performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu

Objective number three of the study was to examine the relationship between project communication and performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu.

The responses in this area are presented, analyzed and discussed below:

Table 4.10: Response on the relationship between project communication and performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu

Response	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Project communication sets in motion the entire process of acquiring a successful performance in Digfer general teaching hospital construction.	109	3.27	1.808	Very Good
Project communication facilitates efficient and effective performance in Digfer general teaching hospital construction.	109	3.21	1.792	Good
There is a relationship between project communication and performance.	109	2.93	1.711	Good
The project communication brings about integration of the diverse decision and activities during Digfer general teaching hospital construction.	109	2.18	1.476	Poor
The project directors ensure availability of funds to run the plans and that it is budgeted for Digfer general teaching hospital construction.	109	2.87	1.694	Good
Average Mean		2.89		Good

Source: Primary Data, 2019

The following mean ranges were used to interpret the means:

For the relationship between project communication and performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu.

Mean Range	Response Mode	Interpretation
3.26-4.00	Strongly agree	Very good
2.51-3.25	Agree	Good
1.76-2.50	Disagree	Poor
1.00-1.75	Strongly disagree	Very poor

From table 4.10 with respect to the relationship between project communication and performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu, this was rated good and this was indicated by the overall average mean of 2.89, hence implying that there is good relationship between project communication and performance of construction project in Mogadishu Somalia. Results in table 4.10 indicated that Project communication sets in motion the entire process of acquiring a successful performance in Digfer general teaching hospital construction and this was rated very good and indicated by the mean of 3.27, which implies that Project communication is a success in setting in motion the entire process of acquiring a good performance in Digfer general teaching hospital construction.

Results further indicated that Project communication facilitates efficient and effective performance in Digfer general teaching hospital construction and this was rated good (mean=3.21), this implied that Project communication facilitates efficient and effective performance in Digfer general teaching hospital construction hence a momentous relationship on both project communication and performance o construction project.

More so the respondents were questioned whether there is a relationship between project communication and performance and this was ranked as good (mean=2.93), however this indicates that since there is a good relationship between project communication and performance there is a great success of the project hence leading to better performance of the construction project.

Results further indicated that the project communication brings about integration of the diverse decision and activities during Digfer general teaching hospital construction was rated poor (mean=2.18), however this implies that the respondents didn't agree that the project communication brings about integration of the diverse decision and activities during Digfer general teaching hospital construction is vital to the success of construction of project.

More so the project directors ensure availability of funds to run the plans and that it is budgeted for Digfer general teaching hospital construction and was rated good as (mean=2.87), this showed that the project directors ensure availability of funds to run the plans and what is budgeted for

Digfer general teaching hospital construction is hence implying a strong relationship between project communication and performance.

Interview Response

Regarding a more understanding on the relationship between project communication and performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu –Somalia, according to one of the Project Supervisor said that,

“The absence of communication within a project presupposes a randomness of behaviour within the performance of construction project. However, the evidence suggests that this is not so. There are patterns of behaviour and a certain consistency and predictability in the way work on construction project is undertaken and the nature of human relationships. It is as a result of this regularity of behaviour that the construction industry has acquired the various stereotypes with which it is associated such as being litigious, antagonistic, under-performing, dangerous and dirty, sexist and discriminatory”.

Furthermore, one of the project managers interviewed said that....

“Lack of purposeful organizational management and inappropriate choice of leadership in have been attributed to some of projects’ failure in school teaching construction projects. Abandoned and failed projects are more predominant which litters every construction project. “On the issue of organizational management, whatever the structure and management process of any organization, the necessary links must be built up between people, and we must learn to accept that employees are not only our greatest and most expensive asset but that they alone are the creators of quality, i.e. people make quality”.

Regarding a more understanding on how has communication played an integral role in keeping the Digfer general teaching hospital construction on task, according to one of the project manager he said that;

“Effective project communication is needed for construction project managers to develop and sustain a competitive advantage for organizational performance and

improvement. Effective project communication is critically important for the potential success of construction projects. Our organisation needs to enact strategies to improve communication that could lead to construction projects success. Improvements in supervisor-subordinate communication will help us towards the goal of managing diversity by promoting equality and improving the performance of construction projects”.

4.4 Description of Dependent variable: Project Performance (n=109)

According to the conceptual framework (figure 2.1), Project Performance was measured in terms of 3 constructs with each contributing items in the data collection instrument (i.e. questionnaire on Project Performance, section C, (appendix I). The constructs are Timeline, Quality output, limited costs, Number of deliverables achieved and Improved service delivery. This is followed by the presentation of findings from qualitative data to corroborate the quantitative findings.

Table 4.11: Gives statistics (i.e. means) on staff self-rating on Project Performance

PROJECT PERFORMANCE	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Finishing project on time	109	3.27	1.808	
Finishing project within the agreed cost	109	3.21	1.792	Very Good
Delivering a project to the agreed scope	109	2.82	1.679	Good
Delivering a project to the agreed quality	109	2.18	1.476	Good
Product acceptance and impact on the customer or end user	109	2.87	1.694	Poor
Effect of the project on the organization to move and prepare for the future	109	3.10	1.761	Good
Project reputation among donors	109	2.87	1.694	Good
National visibility of the project	109	3.10	1.761	Good
Conformity of the goods and services delivered to the project plan	109	2.93	1.711	Good
Average mean		2.60	1.49	Good

Source: Primary Data, 2019

The following mean ranges were used to interpret the means:

Mean Range	Response Mode	Interpretation
3.26-4.00	Strongly agree	Very good
2.51-3.25	Agree	Good
1.76-2.50	Disagree	Poor
1.00-1.75	Strongly disagree	Very poor

From table 4.11 with respect to the dependent construct that is project performance, this rated Good and this was indicated by the overall average mean of 2.60, hence implying that project performances of road construction Project is effectively done. Results in table 4.11 indicated that Finishing project on time and this was rated very good and indicated by the mean of 3.27, which implies that project is finished in time.

Results further indicated Finishing project within the agreed cost and this was rated good (mean=3.21), this implied that Project is finished at the agreed cost hence indicating that the stakeholders are trustworthy.

More so Delivering a project to the agreed scope was ranked as good (mean=2.82), however this indicates that the delivering of a project to the agreed scope makes the beneficiaries happy and proficient of construction of the project.

Results further indicated that Delivering a project to the agreed quality was rated poor (mean=2.18), however this implies that Delivering a project to the agreed quality was weak in response hence ineffectiveness of construction of the project in Mogadishu Somalia. More so Product acceptance and impact on the customer or end user and was rated good as (mean=2.87), this showed that effective Product acceptance and impact on the customer or end user has made Digfer general teaching hospital construction a success when conducting project meets needs of users of these projects.

Results further indicated that the effect of the project on the organization to move and prepare for the future was rated good (mean=3.10), however this implies that the effect of the project on the organization to move and prepare for the future of construction of the project in Mogadishu Somalia. More so Project reputation among donors was rated good as (mean=2.87), this showed

that Project reputation among donors has made Digfer general teaching hospital construction a success during the construction of the project.

Results further indicated that National visibility of the project was rated good (mean=3.10), however this implies that there is effective National visibility of the project construction projects in Mogadishu Somalia. More so Conformity of the goods and services delivered to the project plan and was rated good as (mean=2.93), this showed that Conformity of the goods and services delivered to the project plan thus involvement of the project in the conformity of the project; it helps to improve on gauging the success and overall progress of the project.

4.5 The effect of Formal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu –Somalia

Table 4.12: Results of the effect of Formal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu -Somalia

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.623 ^a	.388	.381	.49354

a. Predictors: (Constant), Project Formal Communication

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	13.874	1	13.874	56.956	.000 ^a
	Residual	21.922	90	.244		
	Total	35.796	91			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Project Formal Communication

b. Dependent Variable: Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.103	.244		4.513	.000

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate			
1	.623 ^a	.388	.381	.49354			
	Project Formal Communication		.629	.083	.623	7.547	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction

Source: Primary Data, 2019

Regression analysis results in the Model Summary table revealed that Project Formal Communication accounted for 38.8% on Project Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, and this was indicated by r-squared of 0.388, implying that to a small extent Project Formal Communication as an aspect of project communication contributes to the Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu Digfer general teaching hospital construction. The ANOVA table indicated that Project Formal Communication as a system of project communication significantly affects the Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, and this was indicated by the F-value=56.956 and Sig-value=.000, since the sig. value (0.000) was less than 0.05 and which is the maximum level of significance required to declare a significant effect. This implies that Project Formal Communication as an aspect of project communication highly contributes to the Project Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction. The coefficients table indicated that considering the standard error, Project Formal Communication significantly influence the Project Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction ($\beta=0.629$, Sig=0.000).

Decision on hypothesis

The hypothesis was rejected since the significant value was found to be less than 0.05 (Sig=0.000). Implying that there is no significant relationship between Formal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu –Somalia.

4.6 Effect of Informal Communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu -Somalia

Table 4.13: Results of Effect of Informal Communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu -Somalia

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.473 ^a	.224	.215	.55553

a. Predictors: (Constant), Informal communication

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8.021	1	8.021	25.992	.000 ^a
	Residual	27.775	90	.309		
	Total	35.796	91			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Informal communication

b. Dependent Variable: Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.326	.315		4.207	.000
	Informal communication	.562	.110	.473	5.098	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction

Source: Primary Data, 2019

Regression analysis results in the Model Summary table indicated that the Informal communication accounted for 22.4% on Project Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction and this was indicated by r-squared of 0.224, implying that Informal communication as a system of project communication significantly contributes 22.4% on the Project Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction. The ANOVA table indicated that Informal

communication significantly affects the Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction and this was indicated by the F-value=25.992 and Sig-value=.000, since the sig. value (0.000) was less than 0.05 and which is the maximum level of significance required to declare a significant effect. This implies that Informal communication as a system of project communication highly affects the Project Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction. The coefficients table indicated that considering the standard error, Informal communication significantly affects the Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction ($\beta=0.562$, Sig=0.000).

Decision on hypothesis

The hypothesis was rejected since the significant value was found to be less than 0.05 (Sig=0.000). Implying that there is no significant relationship between Informal Communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu –Somalia.

4.7 The influence of communication channels on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu

Table 4.14: Results of the influence of communication channels on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.780 ^a	.609	.604	.39451

a. Predictors: (Constant), Communication channels

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	21.788	1	21.788	139.990	.000 ^a
	Residual	14.008	90	.156		
	Total	35.796	91			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Communication channels

b. Dependent Variable: Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.780 ^a	.609	.604	.39451

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.672	.193		3.476	.001
	Communication channels	.741	.063	.780	11.832	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction

Source: Primary Data, 2019

Regression analysis results in the model Summary table indicated that the Communication channels significantly affects Project Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction at a rate of 60.9%, and this was indicated by r-squared of 0.609, hence implying that Communication channels significantly influences the Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction. The ANOVA table indicated a positive significant effect Communication channel has on Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction and this was indicated by the positive Beta=0.741 and Sig-value=.000, since the sig. value (0.000) was less than 0.05 and which is the maximum level of significance required to declare a significant effect. This implies that Communication channels highly affect the Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction. Still this implied that high levels of Communication channels improve the level of Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction and poor Communication channels measures reduce it. The coefficients table indicated that considering the standard error, Communication channels significantly affects the Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction ($\beta=0.741$, Sig=0.000).

Decision on hypothesis

The hypothesis was rejected since the significant value was found to be less than 0.05 (Sig=.000). Implying that there is no significant relationship between communication channels on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu.

4.8 Multiple Linear Regression

Table 4.15: Multiple Linear Regression analysis between the Independent and dependent Variables

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.440 ^a	.506	.612	.13191

a. Predictors: (Constant), Formal Communication, Informal communication, Communication channels

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.271	3	1.757	5.168	.001 ^a
	Residual	2.192	126	.017		
	Total	7.464	129			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Formal Communication, Informal communication, Communication channels

b. Dependent Variable: Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.173	.184		8.254	.000
	Informal communication	.469	.057	.089	4.759	.000
	Communication channels	.513	.034	.499	3.733	.001
	Formal Communication	.403	.032	.483	2.840	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction

Source: Primary Data, 2019

Regression analysis results in table 4.8 revealed that project communication accounted for 61.2% on Project Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction and this was indicated by adjusted r squared of 0.612, this implies that project communication significantly affect the Project Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, and this is indicated by the F-value=0.513, and Sig=0. 001. The coefficients table indicated that of all the aspects of project communication, Informal communication accounted for the biggest influence on Project Performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction ($\beta=0.513$, Sig=0. 001).

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusions

5.1.1 The effect of Formal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu –Somalia

In conclusion the research has shown that, formal communication strongly affects the performance of professionals within the Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu –Somalia. Therefore, clearly establishing and managing the structures of formal communication on project must always be on the agenda of team leaders and management before the commencement of every project.

The study also concludes that the reasons for Formal Communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu –Somalia includes developing a strategy that would deliver the project goals and that the critical dimensions of time, cost, quality and scope can never be attained if a project plan is not in place.

It is an institutionalized activity comprising of a series of predetermined and coordinated actions and processes for carrying out the identification, preparation, appraisal and implementation of projects.

5.1.2 Effect of Informal Communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu -Somalia.

The study concludes that since Informal Communication means to learn in a surrounding where a person is directed to be involved in learning process informally.

Learning becomes a part of his/her work on non-regular basis. This form of communication is concerned with the daily routine activities of work, with family or with friends or leisure time. In Informal Communication the communicator is not even aware of the fact that he/she is learning. This learning becomes the part of his/her skills, behavior and attitude.

Furthermore, as Informal Communication is associated with individuals within an organization, so a change in behavior, skills and attitude of these individuals ultimately impacts on the

organizational output. Its productivity and performance are improved by the aid of improved performance of employees associated with Informal Communication. Organization spends a considerable amount of money on formal sessions, like meetings, training programs, sessions, seminars etc., but these organizations do not consider Informal Communication as an important factor towards their development. There is, nowadays, somehow awareness about such type of communication which is going to be fruitful for Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu -Somalia.

5.1.3 The influence of communication channels on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu

The study concludes that within the Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu, there is a strong appreciation of the importance of project communication and its importance within the project. Indeed, various levels and channels of communications have been established within the construction industry, for example communication between the clients and consultants or consultants and contractors. In spite of that, there have been many hindrances to effective communication channels on Digfer general teaching hospital construction, in Mogadishu, Somalia. These includes; poor listeners, poor leadership, unclear communication objectives, unclear channels of communication, ineffective reporting system, ineffective communication between the parties on the project, stereotyping and language difficulties. Finally, the research established that poor communication had resulted in project delays, project cost overrun and project abandonment.

5.1.4 The relationship between project communication and performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu

The study concludes that within the Digfer General Teaching Hospital Construction there is good relationship between project communication and performance of construction project in Mogadishu Somalia, hence implying that, project communication strongly affects the performance of professionals within the construction industry. Therefore, clearly establishing and managing the structures of communication on project must always be on the agenda of team leaders and management before the commencement of every project.

Since the implication of strong relationship between the two variables it is to the project sponsors and champions to ensure that other project stakeholders have been provided with and are satisfied with the availed project information, the efforts (both financial and otherwise) invested into construction projects could be seen as having been fruitless. In the same vein, where project supervisors are not as attentive to their subordinates' views and no appropriate avenues have been designated to capture feedback from implementers' and beneficiaries of the project, there will be a high chance of failure of construction project.

5.2 Recommendations

In line with the findings, discussions and the conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were drawn;

5.2.1 The effect of Formal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu –Somalia

Although there was clear distinction between the agreements and disagreements of the formal communication, it is therefore recommended that Digfer General Teaching Hospital Construction, formal communication should be compared with traditional communication tools based on criteria for efficient communication. A self-hosted formal communication platform should be chosen to avoid sensitive information leakage. By comparing these two communication tools, the efficiency of each tool will be exposed. By exposing communication tools' efficiency, the impact on communication performance will be further demonstrated hence effective performance of the project.

5.2.2 Effect of Informal Communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu -Somalia.

The study recommends that Informal communication should be viewed as important and integral part of an organizational culture. Where the Organizations should encourage an atmosphere of informal communication.

Organizations must have to conduct seminars and sessions in order to make employees aware of the importance and applicability of informal learning in the course of individual and organizational development.

Organizations must create a platform where employees would express and demonstrate the informally learnt skills in their daily jobs.

Employees who are not aware of the significance of informal communication be counseled, inspired and motivated to be part of life-long learning processes.

5.2.3 The influence of communication channels on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu

The study recommends that to provide and endure with project success, project implementers should ensure that communication to all project participants and stakeholders as regards to what is happening is effectively conducted. A clear channel of communication preferred by the majority within the project should be used such that there are no complaints and conflicts developing during the project life cycle. Additionally, Project managers should also orient employees on how project communication is going to be conducted, do thorough, analysis of information flow charts within the entire project, awareness campaigns concerning how the works should react to particular forms of communication, and ensuring that due feedback channels are well established. Finally in an attempt to have the best success on projects, there is also need to establish strong internal communication structures and processes to facilitate stakeholders to succeed in carrying out their tasks. Project information systems need to be developed, policy manuals and clear flow charts culture and above all making clear and proper communication as part of the organization culture.

5.2.4 The relationship between project communication and performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu

In line with the finding that a strong positive relationship exists between project communication and performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, project directors, project coordinators, project supervisors and project managers who comprise the construction project team, ought to communicate activities that they require their staff to do, in an effective manner. This is likely to be in ways including but not limited to actively listening to their recipient's point of view. There is need to ensure that resourceful persons like the top management in the various teaching hospital involved in execution of construction project, give due support to construction project. This should be in ways that include prompt release of funds meant for such activities, top

management scrutiny of reports about progress of such projects and increasingly participating in their implementation.

Since the findings revealed a strong positive relationship between individual commitment and perceived project performance, the Project managers in charge of construction projects in Diger General Teaching Hospital ought to ensure commitment of project staff to achievement of objects by creating an atmosphere of feeling like they (project staff) are part of the family of the project implementation team. This could be through fulfilling the promises that top management sets forth. In this way, the various stakeholders involved in implementation are likely to perceive the project as a success.

5.3 Contributions of the study to the existing body of knowledge

The study was able to bridge gap drawing up on the argument that, the performance of firms is highly increased when individuals shared information, lessons, best practices, experiences, insights and common grounds. Although, it couldn't able to justify the above theory based on the empirical analysis, all the responders agree about the knowledge sharing process among the discussion of employees about issues. One of the examples is the interview of respondent, he mentioned that there are always facts in the mind of the people that wants to share them with other, he suggests that informal communication is more favorable to share ideas than formal one. Considerable research conducted by (Renzil, 2016), depict that formal and informal knowledge sharing is different in regards to frequency of interaction and closeness of an individual in knowledge sharing process. I couldn't confirm this theory based on the empirical analysis; however, the respondents generally suggest the knowledge experience is shared by either formal or informal communication both in and outside the project. In general, all respondents believe knowledge can be shared especially in the case of informal communication inside the project team and among the stakeholders and the politicians of the region.

5.4 Areas of Further Research

This study used a single research methodological approach and future research thorough interviews could be undertaken to broaden the perspective. The standard questionnaire limited the ability to collect views about information outside the standard questions. The study dimensions were realistically only proxies for an underlying embryonic phenomenon which may render them

not very appropriate for studies. Further research should look at; 1) information sharing, risk management and performance of projects in universities. 2) Teamwork, ethics and project performance in organizations. 3) Procurement management and performance of projects.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX I: QUESTIONNAIRE FOR PROJECT STAFF (CASUAL LABOURERS)

I am **SHUKRI ABDIKARIM SAID, Reg No. FEB 2023**, a student of Accord University pursuing a Master's Degree in **Project Management**. This questionnaire is designed to collect information aimed at finding out "**PROJECT COMMUNICATION AND PERFORMANCE OF DIGFER GENERAL TEACHING HOSPITAL CONSTRUCTION IN MOGADISHU - SOMALIA**". The information obtained will be strictly for academic purposes and it will be treated with utmost confidentiality. I kindly request you to fill this questionnaire. Please tick in the space provided.

Thank you v much for your time and co-operation

Instructions

- (i) Tick in the box provided.
- (ii) Fill in the spaces provided

Section A (i): DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

1. Sex

- i. Male
- ii Female

2. Age

- 20-25
- 26-30
- 31-36
- 41 above

3. Marital status:

- Married
- Divorced
- Widow
- Single

4. Education:

- i. Certificates

ii. Diploma

iii. Bachelors

iv. Masters

5. Working experience

0- 1 year

2-3 years

4-6 years

5 years and above

SECTION B. Formal communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu -Somalia.

Kindly tick as the statement below are applicable to you, using the provided key below.

SA: Strongly Agree

A: Agree

D: Disagree

SD: Strongly disagree.

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD
1	The project manager's major responsibility is to build supportive social networks (collaborative relationships) among a diverse group of stakeholders.				
2	Successful project management formal communication is about being there for everyone, being in touch with the real challenges of the project, understanding the real issues within the team who must deliver the project				
3.	Formal Communication must circulate through the project management teams of Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu, and external stakeholders to maintain the health and the viability of the project				
4.	Project managers handling the Digfer general teaching hospital construction In Mogadishu should be mindful of any cultural differences among team members and other stakeholders that could result in miscommunication.				
5.	Formal Communication plays an integral role in keeping a project on task				
6.	project communication acts as a connecting factor that links the various stakeholders of the projects like the Digfer general teaching hospital construction in Mogadishu				
7.	The project manager is charged with guiding all aspects of the project, including the formal communication plan				
8.	Formal Communication may mean being able to talk, speak and be listened to.				

SECTION C: Informal Communication on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu -Somalia.

To what extent do you agree with each of the following statements?

Rank by placing a tick in the appropriate column.

SA: Strongly Agree

A: Agree

D: Disagree

SD: Strongly disagree.

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD
1	Informal Communication has clarified project tasks, created teamwork and got all stakeholders involved in the running of the Digfer general teaching hospital construction				
2	Informal communication effects working with our supervisors so as to perform more in our duties.				
3.	Informal communication has to a very large extent been used to determine our level of performance at work in the company.				
4.	Informal Communication has increased the level of commitment of workers in an organization, and this may be the case under normal circumstances				
5.	Informal Communication has imposed increased responsibilities that have made our construction job more valuable and important.				
6.	Construction staff with more work experience have more respect for their jobs, can apply their experience to their jobs, and are skilled and successful in doing their jobs				
7.	Informal Communication has provided technical support and guidance to project staff of Digfer general teaching hospital construction				
8.	Informal Communication is recognized to be a significant, but complex, multidimensional predictor of job satisfaction in Digfer general teaching hospital constructions				

SECTION D: The influence of communication channels on performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu

To what extent do you agree with each of the following statements?

Rank by placing a tick in the appropriate column.

SA: Strongly Agree

A: Agree

D: Disagree

SD: Strongly disagree.

S/N	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD
1	Communication channels in Digfer general teaching hospital construction means the communication between the project and its relevant environment, typically the client and end-user				
2	Communication channels is effective within the working group in the construction industry in Somalia				
3.	Communication channels within the Digfer general teaching hospital construction group is effective based on the key factors like; Past experiences, Education and Intellectual difference				
4.	Project communication channel management is vital to the success of constructional projects				
5	The operations in Digfer general teaching hospital construction involve the team effort of clients, quantity surveyor, architect, consulting engineer and project specialists is strengthen by the communication channels				
6	Communication channels plans and strategies must be determined /established at the outset				

Section E: The relationship between project communication and performance of Digfer general teaching hospital construction, Mogadishu

To what extent do you agree with each of the following statements?

Rank by placing a tick in the appropriate column.

SA: Strongly Agree

A: Agree

D: Disagree

SD: Strongly disagree.

	ITEM	SA	A	D	SD
1	Project communication sets in motion the entire process of acquiring a successful performance in Digfer general teaching hospital construction.				
2	Project communication facilitates efficient and effective performance in Digfer general teaching hospital construction.				
3	There is a relationship between project communication and performance.				
4	The project communication brings about integration of the diverse decision and activities during Digfer general teaching hospital construction.				
5	The project directors ensure availability of funds to run the plans and that it is budgeted for Digfer general teaching hospital construction.				

SECTION F:

1. Please tick the appropriate box depending on your level of agreement or disagreement as arranged in the 5 Likert Scale:

1	2	3	4
Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree

NO	PROJECT PERFORMANCE	1	2	3	4
1	Finishing project on time				
2	Finishing project within the agreed cost				
3	Delivering a project to the agreed scope				
4	Delivering a project to the agreed quality				
5	Product acceptance and impact on the customer or end user				
6	Effect of the project on the organization to move and prepare for the future				
7	Project reputation among donors				
8	National visibility of the project				
9	Conformity of the goods and services delivered to the project plan				

Thank you for your participation

**APPENDIX II: INTERVIEW GUIDE FOR PROJECT MANAGERS, PROJECT
SUPERVISORS AND PROJECT COORDINATORS**

1. What do you understand by the term Project Communication?
2. Does communication exist among your organization team members?
3. Has communication helped the project teams to perform to their best?
4. How has communication played an integral role in keeping the Digfer general teaching hospital construction on task?
5. What limitations have you faced in implementing effective communication in your construction company?
6. What is the major source of funding for your project (Digfer general teaching hospital construction)?
7. How do wages and salaries motivate project employees to improve on their performance towards Digfer general teaching hospital construction?
8. How can supervision by project managers in Digfer general teaching hospital construction improve on project performance
9. In what ways can remuneration of project employees improve on project performance?
10. How can marital status of project employees influence project performance?
11. How has the educational level of employees in Digfer general teaching hospital construction improved on project performance?
12. How has the work experience of employees on construction projects improved on project performance and success of projects?
13. Do you have anything else you would want to tell me apart from what is asked above?
Yes or No, If yes mention it?

Thank you for responding to my questions